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УПРАВЛЕНИЕ ЧЕЛОВЕЧЕСКИМИ РЕСУРСАМИ: КРОСС-КУЛЬТУРНЫЙ МЕНЕДЖМЕНТ

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HUMAN RESOURCE MANAGEMENT: CROSS-CULTURAL MANAGEMENT

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Аннотация

Неотъемлемым звеном для успешного развития бизнеса в условиях повсеместной глобализации является кросс-культурный менеджмент. В современных условиях руководители и менеджеры должны быть готовы к международному взаимодействию как внутри бизнеса, так и за его пределами.

Abstract

Cross-cultural management is an integral link for successful business development in conditions of wide-spread globalization. In modern conditions, managers and managers should be ready for international cooperation both inside and outside the business.

Ключевые слова: менеджмент, принятие управленческих решений, управление человеческими ресурсами; кросс-культурный менеджмент.

Keywords: management, management decision-making, human resource management; cross-cultural management.

Introduction

Conducting research and taking into account the characteristics and patterns inherent in different business cultures in management is the fundamental goal of cross-cultural management. Knowledge of such features helps to determine mutual understanding and effective communication between representatives of different business cultures. The use of cross-cultural human resource management means the effectiveness of external and internal communications.

In modern realities, there is probably no longer a person who is unfamiliar with the concept of globalization or who denies its ubiquity. The strategic plans of most companies are now focused on adapting to the conditions of globalization, and business giants have been successfully operating in them for a long time. At the same time, globalization for an organization is not only a modification of business plans, but also a completely different, new approach to human resource management. In this regard, cross-cultural management deals with the problems and issues of the interpenetration of cultures in the business sphere, and this is the relevance of this topic.

The study of the modern understanding of the concept of "cross-cultural management" is the main purpose of the article.

The main tasks considered in this article are the study of primary relevant sources and drawing up a picture of the real and desired level of implementation of cross-cultural management in human resource management.

The scientific novelty lies in the practical application of the processes of cross-cultural interaction in human resource management.

Human resource management is directly related to the concept of cross-cultural management, since basically this term implies direct work with human resources.

The use of cross-cultural management techniques is an integral link not only for international business, rather, for them it is still a mandatory factor, but also for small and medium-sized businesses, local organizations. The market is developing quite rapidly and often unpredictably, so, for example, a company can unexpectedly find a partner abroad. And how, then, in this case, to build relations with foreign colleagues?

First of all, the sphere of cross-cultural management should begin directly with the education and enlightenment of managers, since they are the face and representation of the organization in any external interaction, and also show an example to their subordinates.

It is the management that has the authority to implement the policy and principles of competent intercultural interaction in companies. In view of this, the direct head of the organization should be the leader of the entry of companies into the world of globalization. To do this, various trainings and educational programs for managers are being implemented very successfully.

Since we are talking about educational programs and trainings, the next step that needs to be taken is the education of all the company's personnel, with regard to the peculiarities of cultures and proper interaction with them. The problem of misunderstanding of cultures can be faced by both the manager and employees in direct interaction with another company, or when hiring a foreigner, that is, a person of another culture. Such a person can fully meet all the necessary competencies and be an excellent performer, but at the same time have any cultural characteristics that are incomprehensible to the manager, manager or colleagues. However, this should not be a reason for the dismissal of this employee, or refusal to hire. That's exactly why it is extremely important for absolutely all levels of managers and their subordinates to have a basic understanding of the life and mentality of other countries and cultures. Especially in conditions of large migration waves, when hiring a foreigner is no longer something unusual.

The situations described above assume that these actions take place on our territory and under our conditions. But do not forget that companies quite often send their employees on business trips or internships to other countries. This circumstance assumes that such employees have two groups of skills at once:

1. knowledge of a foreign language, and first of all - English. Let's not dispute the fact that English is the business language spoken by all international organizations, that is, it is the world language. In this regard, in the issue of human resource management, it is very important to understand that without knowledge of a foreign language, employees, and even more so company managers, simply have nothing to do in the business sphere of the XXI century. In most companies, proficiency in English is one of the fundamental requirements for candidates for a position. But at the same time, knowledge of a foreign language implies constant practice, in this regard, the top management of companies needs to provide conditions for training and maintaining the skills of their employees.

2. for the company's employees, it is necessary to conduct a test or exam for knowledge of the cultural characteristics of a particular country before their direct departure there. An employee of a company, being on the territory of another country and a specific organization, being its representative, can make a great impression and establish long-term long-term plans for cooperation, or spoil all the agreements between them. This is especially important during negotiations, when signing a contract or promising cooperation is at stake, and then even a minor oversight in communication can put an end to the possibility of a favorable outcome. For an employee with the skill to successfully conduct international negotiations, it is an undoubted advantage over the rest of the company's participants. But what should all other employees do in this situation? And managers

should deal with this issue and thereby ensure the formation of personnel.

Business cooperation with representatives of other cultures can occur not only through direct live contact, but also through business correspondence. Undoubtedly, all employees of the company should have the skills of business correspondence. And if everyone has figured out the usual correspondence at the moment and mastered its subtleties, then conducting a dialogue in conditions of cross-cultural communications is not so widespread yet. This includes, as mentioned above, knowledge of a foreign language in business correspondence, and knowledge of the rules of email correspondence abroad. Training in these skills should also be provided to top managers.

In addition to the topic of education, the problem of interethnic conflicts and discrimination should also be touched upon. Despite additional training, a certain part of the personnel still has a misunderstanding of other cultures. It is extremely important for both managers and managers to anticipate such situations and be able to solve them competently. Undoubtedly, managers themselves should understand all the subtleties of the cultures of their colleagues and subordinates well, so as not to make a decision that discriminates against them themselves. But even here it is very important for managers and top managers to see the border and try not to overdo it with their political correctness. Recently, there have been more and more situations in companies when some minorities have tried to give certain privileges so that they do not feel violated, but at the same time they have gone too far with their good intentions, creating conditions that are unfair to the rest of the team.

The clash of cultures is not only the cultures of different countries or nationalities, but also corporate ones. This difference is particularly noticeable during negotiations. Quite often, it is extremely difficult to make a common decision even for residents of the same country, since companies can have extremely different ways of doing business. In this regard, to conduct international negotiations, companies should hire a specially trained employee, and preferably on a permanent basis. Nevertheless, even with such a specialist in the company, other employees also need to possess basic skills and techniques of successful negotiations.

Recently, the heads of many companies have increasingly resorted to the services of outside trainers or, as they are now called, coaches to conduct various trainings, tests and master classes. The most common of them at the moment is testing for emotional intelligence (EQ). It is precisely such employees who should represent the interests of the company at negotiations or various debates, conferences. It is believed that people who have a high EQ coefficient are much easier to adapt to changing circumstances, adapt to the interlocutor faster and are able to read his real emotions, and, accordingly, his opinion.

Conclusion

The ideal employee of 2022 is a person who knows how to negotiate effectively, be tolerant and understanding, speak a foreign language and be ready for continuous training. And yet people are not robots, but

the concept of "ideal employee" is just a utopia for an employer. The manager is quite capable of doing some things to bring his company's employees closer to this ideal. Based on all of the above, the company's management should:

First, start with self-study, that is, get the first all the skills and knowledge that he expects and requires from his employees. Thus, he will show them by his own example what skills and knowledge an employee of this company should have.

Secondly, to prepare the company's personnel for cross-cultural interaction by organizing courses for employees in a foreign language and gaining knowledge about other cultures.

Thirdly, to develop the necessary skills, both for yourself and for your employees. For example, the ability to conduct negotiations and business correspondence.

Fourth, for a large company to take a specialist in negotiations and interaction into the main staff, if the company is small, to train its employees.

Fifth, conduct various trainings and tests on a regular basis to better understand the processes within the organization and the team, as well as timely highlight

someone's special qualities and potential for their effective application in business.

Effective management can always easily adapt to the rapidly changing conditions of cross-cultural business, but now it is also necessary to train its employees to comply with these changes.

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ОСОБЕННОСТИ МЕТОДИКИ РАСЧЕТА ЗАТРАТ НА ОБЕСПЕЧЕНИЕ СРЕДСТВАМИ ИНДИВИДУАЛЬНОЙ ЗАЩИТЫ РАБОТНИКОВ ПРЕДПРИЯТИЙ

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FEATURES OF THE COST CALCULATION METHODOLOGY TO PROVIDE PERSONAL PROTECTIVE EQUIPMENT EMPLOYEES OF ENTERPRISES

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Аннотация

Затраты на обеспечение средствами индивидуальной защиты работников являются неотъемлемой частью совокупных затрат на охрану труда. Средства индивидуальной защиты предназначены для защиты и предотвращения производственных травм, заболеваний и несчастных случаев на объектах производства.

Abstract

The costs of providing workers with personal protective equipment are an integral part of the total labor protection costs. Personal protective equipment is designed to protect and prevent industrial injuries, diseases and accidents at production facilities

Ключевые слова: средства индивидуальной защиты, затраты, охрана труда.

Keywords: personal protective equipment, costs, labor protection.

В целях защиты работников от несчастных случаев и профессиональных заболеваний на предприятиях с вредными и опасными условиями труда

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